

**Action of different Ring-closing Agents upon 4-R-Thio-
semicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates and 4-R-semicar-
bazide-dithiocarboxylates: Formation of different
Types of Thiobiazoles and Oxybiazoles.**

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Methyldithiocarbazine was first prepared by Busch (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1916, 93, 59), and in the same paper he described mono- and di-alkyl-dithiocarbazines of the type $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{SR}$ and $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{N} : \text{C} (\text{SR}) \cdot \text{SR}'$ respectively. In the present paper a thorough and systematic study of methyldithiocarbazine as regards its action upon different carbimides and thiocarbimides has been made and the resulting semicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates and thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates have been subjected to the action of different ring-closing agents, *e.g.*, hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide solution, acetic anhydride, etc.

Thiocarbimides and carbimides react with the active hydrazino part of the methyldithiocarbazine to yield 4-R-thiosemicarbazide-1-methyldithiocarboxylates and 4-R-semicarbazide-1-methyldithiocarboxylates, thus:—

Phenyl-, tolyl-, xylyl-, allyl-isothiocyanates and phenyl- and naphthyl-isocyanates have thus yielded respectively the corresponding thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates (I, II, III, IV, see pp. 163, 166, 168 and 169) and semicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates (V, VI).

The ring-closure of the above 4-R-thiosemicarbazide-1-methyldithiocarboxylates has been found to be really interesting. Phenylthiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate loses one molecule of hydrogen sulphide when it is heated with alcohol with

the formation of 2-phenylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole, thus:

The same compound (VII) is also obtained when an aqueous solution of methylthiosemicarbazate hydrochloride is boiled with phenyl mustard oil. Presumably, 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide-1-methyl-dithiocarboxylate is formed and loses a molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen.

By the action of acetic anhydride, the acetyl derivative of compound (VII) is formed, and this can be hydrolysed so as to yield compound (VII).

By the action of hydrochloric acid upon phenylthiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate, a molecule of aniline is split off and there is formed 2-thio-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole, thus:

Ring-closure of phenylthiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate has also been effected with sodium hydroxide solution. In this case however, the ring-closure is attended with the elimination of a molecule of methyl mercaptan. Thus there is formed 2-phenylimino-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole:—

This compound was prepared by Freund and Imgart (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 956) from $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NHPh}$ by boiling with

concentrated hydrochloric acid and they wrongly called it phenyl-dithiourazole. Guha prepared a large number of such R-imino-thiol-thiobiazoles from $\text{RNH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}_2$ and carbon bisulphide in presence of potassium hydroxide (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1510).

The action of tolyl mustard oil upon methylthiocarbazine is peculiar and takes two different courses depending upon whether the solvent is taken in large or small quantity.

With a small quantity of alcohol, there is formed 4-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide-1-methylthiocarboxylate, and with a larger quantity, there is formed 2-tolylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thio-diazole (X).

Xylyl (and allyl) mustard oil reacts with methylthiocarbazine to give a mixture of 4-R-thiosemicarbazide-1-methylthiocarboxylate and 2-R-imino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thio-diazole of which the former is soluble in alkali whilst the latter is not.

The actions of acetic anhydride, hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide upon the tolyl, xylyl, and allyl compounds (II, III, IV) are exactly similar to those as observed with the corresponding phenyl compound (I) and thus compounds (XI—XVII) are formed.

Acetic anhydride reacts with phenyl and naphthyl semicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates (V and VI) to yield 2-R-imino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-oxdiazoles (XVIII, XIX), thus:

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-1-methylthiocarboxylate, $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}_2\text{Me}$ (I).

Methylthiocarbazine (6 g.) was dissolved in warm absolute alcohol and phenyl mustard oil (7 g.) was gradually added and the mixture was continually shaken. The solution was allowed to stand overnight when a white precipitate was found to have formed which was filtered and crystallised from alcohol. The yield before crystallisation was quantitative but after crystallisation the yield was 10 gms., the loss being due to the formation of a ring compound, which remained in the mother-liquor. It melts at $143^\circ\text{--}144^\circ$ with

decomposition. Busch (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1916, 93, 360) gives m. p. 136°-137°. (Found: N, 16·14. $C_6H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires N, 16·34 per cent.)

2 - *Phenylimino -5-methylthiol-2:3 - dihydro - 1:3:4 - thiodiazole* (VII).—The alcoholic mother-liquor from the above experiment was concentrated to half its bulk and treated with an equal volume of water. The white precipitate was crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 132°-133°. It is extremely soluble in alcohol but insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 18·41. $C_6H_9N_2S_2$ requires N, 18·83 per cent.)

The Acetyl derivative.—The above substance (1 g.) was heated with an excess of acetic anhydride under reflux for about 20 minutes and then poured into water when an oily mass was obtained which solidified on standing. It was crystallised from water; m.p. 153°-154°. (Found: N, 15·60. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 15·85 per cent.)

Methyldithiocarbazine Hydrochloride and Phenyl Mustard Oil: Formation of (VII).

Methyl-dithiocarbazine (2·48 g.) was dissolved in an excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and phenyl mustard oil (2·8 g.) gradually added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 3-4 hours; on cooling a white solid mass was obtained. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol; m. p. 132°-133°. It is insoluble in dilute caustic soda solution and identical with compound (VII). (Found: N, 18·54. $C_6H_9N_2S_2$ requires N, 18·83 per cent.). Busch and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2247) and Busch and Bichler (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1916, 93, 360) give m. p. 126-127°.

Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate and Acetic Anhydride: Formation of 2-Phenylimino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiobiazols.

Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate (2 g.) was heated on a sand-bath with an excess of acetic anhydride under reflux for 15-20 minutes. The clear solution was poured into water when an oily mass was obtained which on standing solidified and was crystallised from water. Yield 1 gm. It is insoluble in dilute caustic soda solution: m. p. 153°-154°. (Found: N, 15·63.

$C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S_2$, requires N, 15.85 per cent.). It is identical with the acetyl derivative of compound (VII); mixed m. p. 153-154°.

Deacetylation of the above Compound.

The above compound (1 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19) for 20 minutes. On cooling a white solid came down which was crystallised from dilute alcohol. It was identical with compound (VII); m. p. 132°-133°. (Found: N, 18.62. $C_8H_8N_2S_2$, requires N, 18.83 per cent.)

Treatment of Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate with Hydrochloric Acid: Formation of 2-Thion-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiobiazole (IX).

Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate (2 g.) was heated with an excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19) for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture, on cooling, yielded a white precipitate which was crystallised from water in needles; m. p. 143°-144°. Yield 1 gm. It is soluble in cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: N, 17.29. $C_8H_8N_2S_2$, requires N, 17.07 per cent.).

2:5-Dimethylthiol-1:3:4-thiobiazole.

The above substance (0.8 g.) was dissolved in the calculated quantity of sodium hydroxide solution (1 mol. to 1 mol.) and was heated with methyl iodide (0.7 g.) and a few c.c. of methyl alcohol under reflux at 50°-60° for about 15 minutes. After removing the excess of methyl iodide, the solution was poured into water when an oil separated which did not solidify even on standing for several hours. It was then extracted with ether dried over fused calcium chloride, the ether removed and then kept in a vacuum desiccator, where it solidified after a few days and was crystallised from dilute alcohol. It is insoluble in alkali; m. p. 136°; yield 0.1 gm. (Found: N, 15.52. $C_4H_6N_2S_2$, requires N, 15.78 per cent.).

Busch and Ziegele (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, 60, 42) prepared the dimethyl compound by an entirely different method and gave the m. p. 136°. It might be mentioned here that the present method is the only method by which the mono-alkyl-derivatives of the thiobiazoledithiol can be obtained.

Treatment of Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate with Caustic Soda: Formation of 2-Phenylimino-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (X).

Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyl-dithiocarboxylate (2 g.) was heated with 2N-sodium hydroxide solution under reflux. The reaction commenced within a few minutes as was indicated by the evolution of mercaptan. After six hours' heating the evolution of mercaptan ceased and the solution was after cooling acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The white precipitate thus obtained was crystallised from alcohol m. p. 215°-216°. (Found: N, 20·31. $C_8H_7N_3S_2$ requires N, 20·10 per cent.)

The Benzyl derivative.—The above substance (0·2 g.) was dissolved in alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution and was heated with benzyl chloride (0·22 g.) under reflux for 10-15 minutes. A white solid separated out which was washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 140°-141°. (Found: N, 14·21. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S_2$ requires N, 14·05 per cent.)

The Methyl derivative.—The substance (1 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide and heated with methyl iodide (0·5 g.) under reflux at 50°-60° during 20-25 minutes. On pouring into water and standing for some time, a white solid separated which was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol; m. p. 132°-133°. (Found: N, 18·63. $C_6H_9N_3S_2$ requires N, 18·83 per cent.) It is identical with compound (VII).

Methyldithiocarbazine and p-Tolyl Mustard Oil (in a small quantity of alcohol): Formation of 4-p-Tolyl-thiosemicarbazide-1-methyldithiocarboxylate, p-TolNH·CS·NH·NH·CS, Me.

Methyldithiocarbazine (6·1 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of alcohol and tolyl mustard oil (7·5 g.) was gradually added with shaking and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. The separated solid was crystallised in plates from benzene, m. p. 185°-186° (with decomp.). It is soluble in cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The yield is quantitative. (Found: N, 15·78. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S_2$ requires N, 15·50 per cent.)

Methyldithiocarbazine and p-Tolyl Mustard Oil (in a large quantity of alcohol): Formation of 2-Tolylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XI).

Methyldithiocarbazine (8 g.) was dissolved in a large quantity of absolute alcohol and tolyl mustard oil (3·8 g.) gradually

added to it and the mixture kept overnight. No precipitate was found to have separated next day ; but after 4 or 5 days, a crystalline precipitate began to separate slowly with the evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. After a week, the solid product was separated by filtration and crystallised in rectangular plates from dilute alcohol, m. p. 187°-188°. It is insoluble in dilute caustic soda solution. (Found: N, 17·88. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires N, 17·72 per cent.).

Formation of the above compound can be enhanced by concentrating the alcoholic reaction mixture on a water-bath.

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from water. It melts at 94°-95°, and the mixed melting point with the compound obtained from *p*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate and acetic anhydride was also 94-95°. (Found: N, 15·42. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 15·05 per cent.).

Deacetylation of the above Compound.

The acetyl compound was de-acetylated by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the resulting compound was found, by analysis and mixed melting point, to be identical with the compound as obtained by the action of methyl iodide upon compound (XIII). (Found: N, 17·34. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires N, 17·72 per cent.).

Tolyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate and Acetic Anhydride: Formation of 2-Tolylimino-5-methylthiol-3-acetyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XII).

Proceeding in the same way as with the phenyl compound, 1·5 gm. of the thiodiazole derivative was obtained from 2 gm. of the dithiocarboxylate. It melted at 94°-95°. It was proved to be identical with the compound as obtained by acetylating compound (XI). (Found: N, 15·42. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 15·05 per cent.).

Treatment of Tolyl-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate with Hydrochloric Acid: Formation of 2-Thion-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (IX).

The method of procedure was the same as with the phenyl compound. It melted at 143°-144°. It was proved to be identical

with compound (IX) obtained from phenyl-thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate. Presence of toluidine in the acid filtrate was proved.

Treatment of Toly-thiosemicarbazide-methyldithiocarboxylate by Sodium Hydroxide: Formation of 2-Tolylimino-5-thiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIII).

The method of preparation and isolation was the same as in the case of the corresponding phenyl compound (X). It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 215°-216°. (Found: N, 18.77. $C_8H_8N_2S_2$ requires N, 18.83 per cent.).

The Disulphide.—The above thiobiazole compound was dissolved in dilute caustic soda solution and an iodine solution (in potassium iodide) gradually added to it until no more was taken up. The yellow product so obtained could neither be crystallised nor purified from the common organic solvents, it being insoluble in all of them. It was repeatedly washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and water and then dried in a steam oven. It shrinks at 185° and melts at 210°-212°. (Found: N, 18.68. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2S_2$ requires N, 18.92 per cent.).

Methyldithiocarbazinate and Xylyl Mustard Oil: Formation of 4-Xylyl-thiosemicarbazide-1-methyl-dithiocarboxylate (III) and 2-Xylylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XIV).

Xylyl mustard oil (6.5 g.) was gradually added to an alcoholic solution of methyl-dithiocarbazinate (5 g.) under shaking and then allowed to stand for four days without the formation of any precipitate. The solution, on being concentrated on a water-bath, yielded a pasty mass which was treated with cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution in which it was found to be partially soluble. The alkaline filtrate on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a semi-solid mass which soon solidified. The solid could not be isolated in a pure state. So, further investigation was performed with this crude product (yield 2 g.).

2-Xylylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiobiazole.

The insoluble portion was thoroughly triturated with dilute caustic soda solution to remove any trace of the alkali-soluble compound, filtered, washed repeatedly with water and finally

crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 185°-186°; yield 7 gms. (Found :N, 17·19. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S_2$, requires N, 16·73 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared by heating the above compound with an excess of acetic anhydride under reflux for 15 minutes. It was crystallised from water; m.p. 128°-129°. It was proved to be identical with the compound obtained by the action of acetic anhydride upon xylyl-NH·CS·NH·NH·CSSMe. (Found :N, 14·46. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S_2$, requires N, 14·33 per cent.).

Action of Acetic Anhydride upon Xylyl-thiosemicarbaside-dithiocarboxylate: Formation of 2-Xylylimino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XV).

The crude dithiocarboxylate was heated with an excess of acetic anhydride under reflux for 15 minutes. It was then poured into water when an oily mass was obtained which soon solidified and was crystallised from water, m.p. 128°-129°. (Found :N, 14·67. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S_2$, requires N, 14·33 per cent.).

De-acetylation of the foregoing acetyl compound was effected by heating it with concentrated hydrochloric acid. It was identical with the alkali-insoluble compound obtained by the action of xylyl mustard oil upon methyldithiocarbazine; m.p. 185°-186°. (Found :N, 17·20. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S_2$, requires N, 16·73 per cent.).

Treatment of Xylyl-thiosemicarbaside-dithiocarboxylate with Hydrochloric Acid: Formation of 2-Thion-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (IX).

The crude substance was heated with an excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained on cooling was crystallised in needles from water, m.p. 143°-144°. It is soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and is identical with the compound as obtained from phenyl- and tolyl-thiosemicarbaside-methyldithiocarboxylates on similar treatment.

Methyl-dithiocarbazine and Allyl Mustard Oil: Formation of Allyl-thiosemicarbaside-methyldithiocarboxylate (IV) and 2-Allylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XVI).

Allyl mustard oil (5 g.) was gradually added to methyl dithiocarbazine (6 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol and the mixture well shaken and allowed to stand at ordinary temperature for four days.

As no precipitate came out, the solution was almost evaporated to dryness on the water-bath when a semi-solid product was obtained. It was then treated with cold dilute caustic soda solution and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a white precipitate which was purified by crystallisation from water; m.p. 189°-140°; yield 4 gms. (Found: N, 19·39. $C_6H_{11}N_2S_3$ requires N, 19·00 per cent.).

2-Allylimino-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XVI).

The portion insoluble in alkali was washed repeatedly with water and was obtained in long rectangular crystals from boiling water. It shrinks at 75° and melts at 77°-78°. Yield 5 gms. (Found: N, 21·97. $C_6H_9N_2S_4$ requires N, 22·46 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from a small quantity of water. It shrinks at 85° and melts at 93°-94°. It is identical with the compound as obtained by the action of acetic anhydride upon the parent dithiocarboxylate (IV).

Allyl-thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate and Acetic Anhydride: Formation of 2-Allylimino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XVII).

The dithiocarboxylate was heated with acetic anhydride under reflux for 15 minutes and was then poured into water and after some time a solid mass came out which was crystallised from a small quantity of water. It is insoluble in cold dilute caustic soda solution, shrinks at 85° and melts at 93°-94°. (Found: N, 18·63. $C_6H_{11}ON_2S_3$ requires N, 18·84 per cent.).

The *de-acetylation* of compound (XVII) was effected in the usual manner by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the product was crystallised from water in long rectangular plates, m.p. 77°-78°. It was identical with compound (XVI). (Found: N, 22·14. $C_6H_9N_2S_3$ requires N, 22·46 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid upon Allylthiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylate: Formation of 2-Thion-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (IX).

On heating the dithiocarboxylate with concentrated hydrochloric acid a crystalline mass was obtained which was crystallised in needles

from water, m.p. 143°-144°. It is identical with the compound (IX) as obtained similarly from phenyl-, tolyl-, and xylyl-thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates.

Phenyl isocyanate and Methyl-dithiocarbazine: Formation of 4-Phenylsemicarbazide-1-methylthiocarboxylate (V).

From 2 gms. of methyl-dithiocarbazine and 2 gms. of phenyl-isocyanate, 3.8 gm. of the product were obtained. The compound was crystallised from rectified spirit and was soluble in cold dilute alkali. It melts at 197°-198° with decomposition. (Found: N, 17.81. $C_8H_{11}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 17.42 per cent.). Busch (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1916, 93, 351) gives m.p. 190°.

Action of Acetic Anhydride upon the above Compound: Formation of 2-Phenylimino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-oxiazole (XVIII).

The above compound was heated with an excess of acetic anhydride under reflux for 15-20 minutes. It was then poured in water when an oily mass separated out which solidified on standing for some time. The product so obtained was crystallised from water; m.p. 139°-140°. (Found: N, 16.42. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 16.87 per cent.).

Naphthyl isocyanate and Methyl-dithiocarbazine: Formation of 4-Naphthyl-semicarbazide-1-methylthiocarboxylate (VI).

Naphthyl-isocyanate (2.4 g.) was gradually added to an alcoholic solution of methyl-dithiocarbazine (3.3 g.) under vigorous shaking and the mixture was allowed to stand for some time when an insoluble white solid product was obtained. It was crystallised repeatedly from alcohol, m.p. 202°-203° (with decomposition). Yield quantitative. It was soluble in dilute caustic soda solution. (Found: N, 14.21. $C_{13}H_{13}ON_2S_2$ requires N, 14.43 per cent.).

Ring-closure of the above Compound with Acetic Anhydride: Formation of 2-Naphthylimino-3-acetyl-5-methylthiol-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-oxiazole (XIX).

1.5 gm. of a white solid product were obtained by treating 2 gm. of the above compound with acetic anhydride. It was crystallised

from dilute alcohol, m. p. 149°-150°. It was insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 14·46. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 14·05 per cent.).

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